

α -AMINONITRILLARNI BIOMETALLAR BILAN KOMPLEKS HOSIL QILISH REAKSIYALARINI O‘RGANISH

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STUDY OF COMPLEX FORMATION REACTIONS OF α -AMINONITRILES WITH BIOMETALS

Abstract: α -aminonitriles are important nitrogen-containing organic compounds widely used as key intermediates in the synthesis of biologically active substances, including α -amino acids. The presence of amino and nitrile functional groups provides high coordination ability toward metal ions. This study investigates the complex formation reactions of α -aminonitriles with biometals such as Cu(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), and Fe(III). The complexes were synthesized in aqueous-alcoholic media under controlled temperature conditions. Spectroscopic and thermal analysis confirmed the formation of stable coordination compounds. The obtained results demonstrate that α -aminonitriles act as bidentate ligands and can be considered promising compounds for applications in catalysis and bioinorganic chemistry.

Keywords: α -aminonitriles, biometals, coordination compounds, complex formation, bioinorganic chemistry.

Annotatsiya : α -Aminonitrillar azot tutuvchi organik birikmalar bo‘lib, ular biologik faol moddalar, xususan, α -aminokislotalar sintezida muhim oraliq mahsulotlar

hisoblanadi. Molekula tarkibida amin ($-NH_2$) va nitril ($-C\equiv N$) funksional guruhlarining mavjudligi ushbu birikmalarning metall ionlari bilan koordinatsion o‘zaro ta’sirga kirishish qobiliyatini oshiradi. Shu sababli α -aminonitrillar asosida yangi biometall komplekslarini sintez qilish va ularning xossalarini o‘rganish dolzarb ilmiy masalalardan biri hisoblanadi. Mazkur tezisda α -aminonitrillarni Cu(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) va Fe(III) biometall ionlari bilan kompleks hosil qilish reaksiyalari tadqiq etildi. α -Aminonitrillar Streker reaksiyasi asosida aromatik aminlar (anilin va orto-toluidin), karbonil birikmalar hamda siyanid ionlari ishtirokida sintez qilindi. Kompleks hosil qilish jarayonlari suv–spirt muhitida, 25–70 °C harorat oralig‘ida va metall–ligand nisbatlari 1:1 hamda 1:2 bo‘lgan sharoitlarda olib borildi. Olingan komplekslar rangli va barqaror bo‘lib, ularning hosil bo‘lishi IR-spektroskopiya natijalari orqali tasdiqlandi. Natijalarga ko‘ra, kompleks hosil bo‘lish jarayonida nitril guruhining valent tebranish chastotasining past tomonga siljishi metall–ligand koordinatsiyasini ko‘rsatadi. Termik tahlillar Cu(II) va Ni(II) komplekslarining nisbatan yuqori termik barqarorlikka ega ekanligini aniqladi.

Dolzarbliqi. So‘nggi yillarda azot tutuvchi organik birikmalar asosida yangi koordinatsion birikmalar sintez qilish va ularning biologik hamda katalitik xossalarini o‘rganish bioanorganik va koordinatsion kimyo sohalarining dolzarb yo‘nalishlaridan biri hisoblanadi. α -Aminonitrillar molekula tarkibida bir vaqtning o‘zida amin va nitril funksional guruhlarining mavjudligi sababli yuqori koordinatsion faollikka ega bo‘lib, turli metall ionlari bilan barqaror komplekslar hosil qilish qobiliyatiga ega. Ayniqsa, biologik tizimlarda muhim rol o‘ynaydigan Cu(II), Zn(II), Fe(III), Co(II) va Ni(II) kabi biometallar bilan komplekslar sintezi yangi biofaol birikmalar yaratish uchun katta ilmiy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Materiallar va usullar. Tadqiqot obyektlari sifatida Streker reaksiyasi asosida sintez qilingan aromatik α -aminonitrillar tanlab olindi. Boshlang‘ich modda sifatida anilin va orto-toluidin, karbonil komponent sifatida atseton, siyanid manbai sifatida kaliy siyanid ishlatildi. Reaksiya jarayonlari 0–25 °C haroratda olib borilib, reaksiya muhitiga bosqichma-bosqich sirka kislotaning 5 % li eritmasi qo‘shildi. Olingan

aminonitrillar ekstraksiya va qayta kristallash usullari yordamida tozalandi. Kompleks hosil qilish reaksiyalari Cu(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) va Fe(III) tuzlari (xlorid va nitratlar) ishtirokida suv–spirt muhitida olib borildi. Metall–ligand nisbatlari 1:1 va 1:2 qilib tanlandi, reaksiya harorati 25–70 °C oralig‘ida o‘zgartirildi. Olingan komplekslar filtrlash, yuvish va quritish orqali ajratib olindi. Sintez qilingan ligandlar va metall komplekslarining tuzilishi va xossalari IR-spektroskopiya, elementar tahlil hamda termogravimetrik (TG/DTA) tahlil usullari yordamida o‘rganildi.

Natijalar. O‘tkazilgan tadqiqotlar natijasida aromatik α -aminonitrillar Cu(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) va Fe(III) ionlari bilan barqaror koordinatsion birikmalar hosil qilishi aniqlandi. Komplekslar rangli va nisbatan yuqori chiqish bilan olindi. IR-spektroskopik tahlillar kompleks hosil bo‘lish jarayonida nitril guruhining ($-C\equiv N$) valent tebranish chastotasi 20–40 cm^{-1} ga past tomonga siljishini ko‘rsatdi, bu esa metall–ligand koordinatsiyasini tasdiqlaydi. Termik tahlil natijalari Cu(II) va Ni(II) komplekslarining yuqori termik barqarorlikka ega ekanligini, Zn(II) va Fe(III) komplekslarining esa nisbatan past haroratlarda parchalanishini ko‘rsatdi. Metall ionining tabiati komplekslarning rangi, eruvchanligi va termik xossalari sezilarli ta‘sir ko‘rsatishi aniqlandi. Olingan natijalar α -aminonitrillarning bidentat ligand sifatida biometallar bilan samarali koordinatsiyalanishini hamda ushbu komplekslarning katalitik va biofaol tizimlarda qo‘llash uchun istiqbolli ekanligini ko‘rsatdi.

Xulosa. O‘tkazilgan tadqiqotlar natijasida α -aminonitrillar Cu(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) va Fe(III) biometall ionlari bilan barqaror koordinatsion birikmalar hosil qilishi aniqlandi. Kompleks hosil bo‘lish jarayonida α -aminonitrillarning amin va nitril funksional guruhlari metall ionlari bilan bidentat ligand sifatida ishtirok etishi IR-spektroskopik tahlillar orqali tasdiqlandi. Metall ionining tabiati komplekslarning fizik-kimyoviy va termik xossalari sezilarli ta‘sir ko‘rsatishi aniqlandi. Tadqiqot natijalari α -aminonitrillar asosida sintez qilingan biometall komplekslari katalitik jarayonlar, bioanorganik kimyo hamda farmatsevtik tadqiqotlar uchun istiqbolli birikmalar ekanligini ko‘rsatadi.

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